

Multi-Scale Typology of French Territories via Graph Neural Networks

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Abstract

Territorial classification traditionally relies on administrative aggregates that tend to mask the internal heterogeneity of urban fabrics and the complexity of their temporal evolutions. To overcome the inherent limitations of classical partitions (MAUP) and the urban/rural dichotomy, this work explores a morpho-dynamic modeling approach based on geometric deep learning. We propose a hierarchical Graph Neural Network (GNN) architecture adopting a fractal approach to space. The model articulates two representation scales: at the Micro level, the city is understood as a subgraph of grid cells (1 km) capturing the morphological signature and vitality (amenities); at the Macro level, it is integrated as a node in a flow network, capturing its functional interactions and centrality. The central objective is to perform a disentanglement between the relatively stable physical and service support (“the container”) and the variant socio-economic trajectories (“the content”). The model is trained in a self-supervised manner via a reconstruction task of temporally masked attributes, without recourse to pre-existing urban categories. We validate this approach on large-scale urban data covering more than 300,000 buildings at the departmental scale, where the model brings forth coherent spatial structures and fine-grained local dynamics, independent of administrative boundaries. This methodology thus proposes a new lens for interpreting territories, founded on the convergence of form, vitality, and flows.

Keywords: Graph Neural Networks (GNN), Urban Morphology, Spatial Analysis, Self-supervised Learning, Disentanglement, Territorial Typology.

1 Introduction

The classification of territories and the definition of the city constitute persistent challenges in quantitative geography. Classical typologies, often opposing the "urban/rural" binary, currently face a fundamental limit: they rely on average administrative aggregations that erase the internal structure of places. In these models, the city is often reduced to a point or a monolithic polygon, defined by global socio-economic attributes. This work is part of a perspective aimed at overcoming these limitations by adopting what can be described as a "fractal" approach to territorial modeling. The hypothesis explored is that the identity of a city is not a static datum, but an emergent property resulting from the convergence of three complementary dimensions:

1. **Form** (morphology): the physical, topographical, and built container;
2. **Vitality** (amenities): the service content and the supply of facilities that qualify the lived usage of the place;
3. **Flow** (functional): external interactions and relational configurations observed in the urban network.

It is the combination of these dimensions — {Form, Vitality, Flow} — that allows for an understanding of the social function of a place. To operationalize this hypothesis, it is necessary to go beyond standard econometric methods and mobilize models capable of explicitly representing the spatial and relational topology of territories, such as Graph Neural Networks (GNNs). The integration of the geospatial dimension into graphs appears crucial for exploiting neighborhood relations and the shape of entities. Unlike classical vector approaches, *Region Adjacency Graph* (RAG) modeling explicitly structures spatial relations, where each node represents a region and each edge represents contiguity. This structure allows for the description of a topology that simple attribute lists cannot capture. Recent works show, moreover, that the explicit consideration of these neighborhood relations via GNNs improves the classification and characterization of geographical zones. Within this framework, we explore a hierarchical approach aimed at separating, within the representation, the relatively invariant structural components (topography, buildings, facilities) from the more contextual or evolving components (demographics, flows). This perspective falls within a logic of conceptual *disentanglement*, without prejudging a unique or definitive architecture. More precisely, the analysis can be conducted at several scales:

- at a **micro** scale, where territories are represented as local subgraphs (for example, 1 km grid cells), allowing for the extraction of morphological signatures related to form and vitality;
- at a **macro** scale, where these signatures are placed back into a larger graph of interactions and flows, in order to explore the spatial and functional dependencies between territories.

The objective of this work is not to propose a definitive typology of cities, but to establish a methodological framework allowing for the emergence, in a self-supervised manner, of robust territorial regularities, capable of being analyzed, compared, and extended in subsequent works.

2 Related Work

The application of deep learning to geospatial data has long been dominated by Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) applied to regular grids (satellite imagery). However, the irregular nature of administrative partitions and territorial interactions has favored the recent emergence of Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) in quantitative geography.

2.1 Limitations of Traditional Approaches

Classical territorial classification methods (such as Principal Component Analysis or Hierarchical Agglomerative Clustering) rely predominantly on tabular data. These approaches present two major structural limitations that our work aims to overcome. First, they are subject to the Modifiable Areal Unit Problem (MAUP): results depend entirely on an arbitrary administrative partition (the commune) which does not necessarily reflect the functional or morphological reality of places (e.g., a large commune may include both a dense center and agricultural land, blurring the average signal). Second, these statistical models treat observations as independent (i.i.d. hypothesis), ignoring by construction spatial autocorrelation and the topology of the urban network. Yet, in geography, "everything is related to everything else, but near things are more related than distant things" [1]. The absence of explicit neighborhood modeling leads to typologies that lack spatial coherence.

2.2 From Attribute to Geospatial Graph

Traditionally, geographical entities are represented by isolated attribute vectors, ignoring spatial topology. However, recent works demonstrate that structuring these entities as *Region Adjacency Graphs* (RAG) is crucial for capturing contextual dependencies [2]. In this configuration, nodes represent regions and edges represent their physical contiguities, allowing for the modeling of a topology impossible to project onto a simple vector. The explicit integration of this spatial neighborhood significantly improves classification performance, confirming the geographical adage that nearby entities share functional properties.

2.3 Encoding Geometry and Form

While classical GNNs capture topology (connections), they remain agnostic to absolute position and the precise shape of objects (geometry), unless this is manually injected. Several strategies have been proposed to bridge this gap:

- **Positional Encoding:** Inspired by Transformers, certain models like *Spatial GNN* [3] now integrate positional encoders learning a context vector directly from geographical coordinates (x, y) , offering the model an "awareness" of absolute position [4].
- **Polygon Representation:** To go beyond simple scalar descriptors (area, perimeter), approaches like *PolyMP* propose converting the vector geometry of the polygon into a subgraph of vertices [5]. This allows for learning a shape-invariant vector footprint. Our approach draws inspiration from this "subgraph" logic but applies it to a raster mesh (grid cells) rather than vector vertices, to capture the internal texture of the urban fabric.

2.4 Spatial Attention and Flows

Finally, the evolution toward *Graph Attention Networks* (GAT) has allowed for dynamically weighting the influence of neighbors. "Geo-dependent" variants have been introduced to modulate attention not only according to attribute similarity but also according to spatial metrics (distance, shared boundaries) [6]. These mechanisms are essential for modeling asymmetric interactions, where a physical barrier (river, mountain) can cancel the influence of a theoretical contiguity.

3 Data and Territorial Representation

To operationalize the disentanglement between physical form and social dynamics, we build a hierarchical representation of the French territory at two nested scales.

3.1 Micro Level: The City as a Point Cloud (The Content)

At this level, we abandon the vision of the commune as a single point to approach it as a subgraph of elementary cells.

- **Elementary Unit and Graph Construction:** We use the **1km grid cell** (INSEE/Eurostat standard) as the territorial atom. Each commune C_i is represented by a subgraph $G_i = (V_i, E_i)$ where V_i is the set of cells having their maximum surface intersection with the commune. Edges E_i are defined by **Queen contiguity** between the cells. Strict filtering is applied: links do not cross communal boundaries, ensuring that each subgraph is disjoint and internal to its administrative entity.
- **Node Attributes (Cells):** Each node (cell) carries a feature vector divided into two distinct categories:
 1. **Invariant Variables (Structural or Quasi-Structural):** These data describe the physical support, assumed stable in the medium term. They come from the BD ALTI (IGN) and Land Cover (OSO/CLC). They include topography (average altitude, roughness, slope) and soil morphology grouped into 5 meta-classes (Built Structure, Eco, Nature, Agri, Hydrosphere). We also calculate the **local amenity density** (`log_amenity_density`) for each cell. This variable allows the GCN to distinguish, for equal built morphology, a "dormitory" residential neighborhood from a "living" and mixed neighborhood with local services. Although amenity density can evolve in the long term, it is considered here as a quasi-structural component of urban space, reflecting a relatively stable state of development at the considered temporal scale. It is thus used as a proxy for local vitality, intermediate between physical morphology and social uses.
 2. **Variation Variables (Socio-Economic):** These data, from the Filosofi database, capture the state of the system at a time t . They include lived human density, relative wealth (standard of living, poverty), social morphology (share of owners, housing type), and recent demographic dynamics.

3.2 Macro Level: The Urban System (The Context)

The upper level models interactions between communal entities.

- **Nodes (Communes):** The input vector of a macro node is the concatenation of the morphological signature learned at the Micro level (the output *embedding*) and purely macroscopic variables. The latter include:
 - **Flows:** The Autonomy Index (employment) and the Turnover Index (migration).
 - **Centrality [7]:** The **number of structuring facilities** (`nb_equip_structurants`). Expert filtering only retains high-reach services (High schools, Hospitals, Hypermarkets, Administration) to inform the model about the real attraction power of the commune.
- **Multidimensional Edges (Inter-Communal):** Unlike standard binary graphs, we define vector edges $E_{A,B}$ combining four dimensions of interaction:
 1. **Functional Eco:** Home-to-work commuting flows weighted by the active population.
 2. **Functional Residential:** Moving flows weighted by the total population.
 3. **Physical:** Shared Border Length.

4. **Permeability:** Number of roads crossing the border, weighted by road hierarchy (Motorway > Path).

This rich modeling of edges allows the attention mechanism to distinguish real geographical proximity from active functional proximity.

4 Model Architecture: Hierarchical GNN

The proposed architecture relies on a hierarchical processing of information, mimicking the organizational structure of the territory (see Figure 1). The model consists of two successive encoding stages: a local encoder (Micro) and a contextual encoder (Macro), linked by a pooling operation.

Figure 1: **Hierarchical Territorial Representation Architecture.** Conceptual diagram of the proposed architecture. (A) Micro Level: the red circle delimits the subgraph of cells associated with a commune, used to learn a latent representation of its internal structure. (B) Aggregation: compression of the subgraph into a latent vector by a pooling operation. (C) Macro Level: this vector becomes a node in the inter-communal flow graph, allowing for functional contextualization via an attention GNN.

4.1 Stage 1: Morpho-Social Encoder (Micro Level)

The objective of this first stage is to compress the internal complexity of the city (the "point cloud" visible in the red circle of Figure 1.A) into a single latent vector.

- **Input:** For each commune C_i , the model receives the subgraph $G_{micro}^{(i)} = (X_{micro}, A_{micro})$.
 - X_{micro} contains mixed features: physical structure (buildings, topography) and social state (poverty indicators, lived density).
 - A_{micro} is the adjacency matrix describing the contiguity of the cells.
- **Mechanism (GCN):** We apply several layers of graph convolution. At each layer, each cell updates its information by aggregating those of its immediate neighbors (local diffusion of information).

$$H^{(l+1)} = \sigma \left(D^{-1/2} \tilde{A} D^{-1/2} H^{(l)} W^{(l)} \right) \quad (1)$$

where $\tilde{A} = A_{micro} + I$ is the adjacency matrix augmented with self-loops, D is the diagonal degree matrix associated with \tilde{A} , and $W^{(l)}$ is the learnable weight matrix at layer l . This symmetric normalization ensures local propagation of information while preserving the numerical stability of the representations.

4.2 Readout Operation (Aggregation)

This is the pivotal step that performs the change of scale. Once the cells have exchanged information via the GCN, we must summarize the entire communal subgraph into a single signature vector Z_{morpho} . We use a combination of **Mean Pooling** (to capture the general trend, e.g., median income of the territory) and **Max Pooling** (to capture saliencies, e.g., density peak or intense activity zone):

$$Z_{morpho}^{(i)} = \text{MLP} \left(\text{Mean}(H_{final}^{(i)}) \parallel \text{Max}(H_{final}^{(i)}) \right) \quad (2)$$

This vector Z_{morpho} then becomes the intrinsic identity of the city, independent of its absolute geographical position.

4.3 Stage 2: Contextual Encoder (Macro Level)

At this stage, the city is reduced to a node (the red point in Figure 1.C). The objective is now to contextualize this internal signature based on interactions with other cities.

- **Input:** The macroscopic graph where each node i is initialized with its vector $Z_{morpho}^{(i)}$ concatenated with macro-specific variables (Autonomy, Turnover).
- **Mechanism (GAT - Graph Attention Network):** Unlike a simple convolution, we use an attention mechanism here to weight the influence of neighbors. Attention allows the model to handle flow heterogeneity: a city can be geographically close to another but functionally disconnected (physical barrier or absence of flow). The attention coefficient α_{ij} determines the importance city i should give to city j to define its own identity:

$$\alpha_{ij} = \frac{\exp(\text{LeakyReLU}(a^\top [Wh_i \parallel Wh_j \parallel E_{ij}]))}{\sum_{k \in \mathcal{N}(i)} \exp(\text{LeakyReLU}(a^\top [Wh_i \parallel Wh_k \parallel E_{ik}]))} \quad (3)$$

where $\mathcal{N}(i)$ denotes the set of neighbors of city i in the macro graph, and E_{ij} a vector of edge attributes encoding the intensity and nature of interactions between i and j . Softmax normalization guarantees that attention coefficients are comparable between neighbors.

- **Output:** The final vector Z_{final} positions the city in a morpho-dynamic latent space, integrating both what it *is* (Micro) and what it *does* in the system (Macro).

4.4 Self-Supervised Learning

In the absence of a universal "Ground Truth" on city types, we train this model via a proxy reconstruction task: the model randomly masks certain properties of a city (for example, certain aggregated indicators or part of its observed social attributes) and attempts to predict them using only (a) its physical structure and (b) the context of its neighbors. This task does not aim to explicitly model temporal dynamics, but to exploit contextual and structural signals to learn coherent representations from observed states. This constraint forces the network to learn robust correlations between form and function, allowing for an effective final clustering in the latent space Z_{final} . Formally, this proxy task is defined as a partial prediction problem, where a subset of the macroscopic attributes $Y^{(i)}$ of a city i is masked during training. The model is then optimized to minimize a reconstruction loss function \mathcal{L}_{rec} between observed and predicted values, conditional on the latent representation $Z_{final}^{(i)}$ and the neighborhood context. Depending on the nature of the attributes considered, \mathcal{L}_{rec} corresponds to a mean squared error (regression) or cross-entropy (classification).

5 Empirical Results and Emerging Typology

The application of the hierarchical GNN model to all communes in metropolitan France yields a twelve-class typology, structured around the three central components of our approach: *form* (morphological texture), *vitality* (density of local amenities), and *flows* (centrality in movement and migration networks). The average profiles for each cluster are summarized in Table 1. Figure 2 maps the typology across hexagonal France. The qualitative analysis that follows organizes the twelve clusters into four major meta-families: (i) urban cores and command poles, (ii) dense urban belt, (iii) residential peri-urban, and (iv) rural territories, structuring or diffuse.

5.1 Data and Indicators Used

The typology relies on three families of indicators: *form* (morphological texture), *local vitality*, and *flows* (mobility and migration). Unless otherwise stated, the densities used correspond to *lived densities*, i.e., calculated only on the 1 km² cells effectively inhabited. This measure reflects the daily experience of density (proximity to neighbors, building compactness) more than classical administrative densities, which are diluted by non-inhabited spaces. The standard of living is measured by the *median disposable income per consumption unit* (defined in Filosofi). Since the median of a set cannot be obtained by directly combining communal medians, and in the absence of individual micro-data or exhaustive deciles, we proceed with an *approximation via reconstituted distribution*. For each commune, the published quartiles (Q1, Q2, Q3) allow for an approximation of an internal income distribution; these distributions are then aggregated at the cluster level, weighted by consumption units, in order to extract a 50 % quantile. We refer to this quantity as the *approximated median income* to simplify the reading. The hierarchical GNN model combines these micro- and macro-structural indicators within a multi-scale graph, allowing for the learning of common territorial representations. The twelve resulting clusters emerge from this latent space without prior constraints on expected forms.

Table 1: Average profile of the twelve morpho-dynamic clusters

Cluster	Short name	Density (hab./km ²)	Built (%)	Nature (%)	Vitality	Centrality	Ami* (€/CU)	Nb comm.	Pop. (M)
C0	Inhabited rural base	1728	7.7	62.4	0.69	4.7	23,372	7,602	9.8
C1	Quiet res. suburbs	1891	3.7	70.7	0.35	3.3	22,930	4,454	2.8
C2	Dense equipped suburbs	4073	14.3	52.8	1.16	19.4	23,049	3,443	14.4
C3	Regional pivot-cities	1307	12.0	59.0	1.16	4.5	26,552	2,213	3.1
C4	Densified peri-urban	2860	6.2	60.3	0.51	7.2	22,923	3,930	5.9
C5	Secondary metro. centers	8306	11.6	56.2	0.84	20.8	22,875	2,447	11.7
C6	Wealthy forest rural	906	1.8	95.4	0.37	3.1	23,893	1,089	0.5
C7	Wealthy peri-urban	2590	6.9	64.4	0.64	4.3	24,359	3,491	3.9
C8	Metropolitan hyper-centers	6434	30.7	43.9	2.29	32.3	22,789	259	2.2
C9	Specialized dynamic rural	1181	7.3	72.5	0.85	2.2	26,241	819	0.5
C10	Deep and stable rural	1313	3.2	84.4	0.42	2.5	22,151	1,255	0.7
C11	Popular densified countryside	4748	7.7	61.8	0.61	11.6	22,045	3,628	9.7

*Ami: Approximated median income (median disposable income per consumption unit, aggregated by reconstituted distribution).

5.2 Urban cores and structuring poles (clusters C8, C5, C3)

This first family brings together the densest, most equipped, and most central spaces of the territory. It illustrates the model’s ability to disentangle form and function: some centers are extremely dense, others much less so, but all concentrate a high level of centrality and a strong intensity of interactions.

Figure 2: 12-class morpho-dynamic typology across metropolitan France.

Cluster C8: metropolitan hyper-centers. Cluster C8 corresponds to the historical and economic cores of large metropolises (Paris, Lyon, Bordeaux, Lille, Strasbourg, etc.). It constitutes a restricted set (259 communes) but is extremely characteristic. Lived density reaches on average 6,434 hab./km², built density 30.7%, and nature represents only 43.9% of the inhabited cell surfaces. Local vitality is maximal (2.29), as is macro centrality (32.3). The approximated median income remains moderate (22.789 €), reflecting strong internal social heterogeneity. These communes combine residential density, command power, commercial supply, and concentration of structuring facilities. The GNN captures here a notion of *metropolitan centrality* that is reduced neither to density alone nor to standard of living alone.

Cluster C5: secondary metropolitan centers. Cluster C5 groups dense central neighborhoods, often older and socially mixed. Lived density is the highest in the entire typology (8,306 hab./km²), with a built density of 11.6% and nature still present (56.2%). Macro centrality remains very strong (20.8), while local vitality is intermediate (0.84). The approximated median income is around 22.875 €. These communes form a second ring of strong centrality around hyper-centers, more as a continuation of metropolitan functions than as autonomous poles.

Cluster C3: regional pivot-cities. Cluster C3 identifies a coherent set of structuring medium-sized cities (prefectures, university towns, regional poles). Lived density is moderate (1,307 hab./km²) but local vitality is high (1.16), superior to that of most urban belts. Macro centrality is average (4.5) but stable, while the approximated median income is one of the highest in the typology (26.552 €). Despite a lower density than that of dense suburbs, these cities stand out for their role as territorial anchors: they concentrate rare facilities (high schools, hospitals, administrations) and structure their hinterland. The model thus recognizes a functional status that does not automatically follow from density.

5.3 Dense urban belt (clusters C2, C4, C1)

This second family highlights the complexity of the immediate periphery of metropolises. Urban forms there are diverse, ranging from high density to the suburban ring, but all share a functional dependency on the centers.

Cluster C2: dense equipped suburbs. Cluster C2 corresponds to the primary metropolitan rings, typical of restructured large housing estates or dense secondary centers. Lived density reaches 4,073 hab./km², with a built density of 14.3% and nature more present than in hyper-centers (52.8%). Local vitality (1.16) is comparable to that of pivot-cities, and macro centrality remains very high (19.4). The approximated median income (23.049 €) is slightly above the hyper-centers. These spaces combine high residential intensity and a significant supply of amenities. They form a dense living environment but are dependent on hyper-centers for the rarest functions.

Cluster C4: densified peri-urban. With a lived density of 2,860 hab./km², a built density of 6.2%, and nature around 60.3%, cluster C4 describes intermediate ring communes. Local vitality is moderate (0.51) and macro centrality (7.2) indicates the presence of secondary centralities. These are territories where scattered collective housing, compact suburban housing, and small commercial centralities coexist. The model clearly distinguishes them from the wealthier peri-urban (C7) or more forested peri-urban (C6).

Cluster C1: quiet residential suburbs. Cluster C1 groups communes with moderate density (1,891 hab./km²), low built density (3.7%), and significant nature (70.7%). Local vitality is low (0.35) and macro centrality is modest (3.3). The approximated median income (22,930 €) remains close to the national average. The signature is clearly that of a dormitory space: dominant individual housing, some local shops, strong dependency on centers for jobs and structuring facilities.

5.4 Peri-urban and residential countryside (clusters C7, C6)

The peri-urban does not appear as a homogeneous block. The model highlights two distinct trajectories: a wealthy, chosen peri-urban, and a more distant, also favored, forested peri-urban.

Cluster C7: wealthy peri-urban. Cluster C7 presents a lived density of 2,590 hab./km², significant nature (64.4%), and moderate built density (6.9%). Local vitality is intermediate (0.64) and macro centrality is modest (4.3). The approximated median income is high (24,359 €). These are attractive residential peripheries: preserved landscapes, high-quality housing supply, favored social profiles, but strong car dependency. The model identifies a *chosen peri-urban*, distinct both from dense suburbs and deep rural areas.

Cluster C6: wealthy forest rural. With 95.4% nature on average, low lived density (906 hab./km²), and minimal built density (1.8%), cluster C6 corresponds to highly wooded communes, located on the periphery of large urban areas or in forest massifs. Local vitality is low (0.37) and macro centrality limited (3.1), but the approximated median income remains high (23,893 €). These territories extend the wealthy peri-urban into even more natural spaces, halfway between residential countryside and resort rurality.

5.5 Rural territories: structure, intensity, and social gradients (clusters C0, C10, C11, C9)

Finally, the last family groups rural spaces. Far from forming a homogeneous continuum, they are divided here into four distinct profiles, organized according to lived density, local centrality, and demographic dynamics.

Cluster C0: inhabited rural base. The first cluster by its size (7,602 communes and nearly 9.8 million inhabitants), cluster C0 represents the *ordinary rural*. Lived density (1,728 hab./km²) is higher than administrative densities suggest, due to the presence of small towns (bourgs). Nature remains dominant (62.4%), local vitality moderate (0.69), and macro centrality not negligible (4.7). The approximated median income is 23,372 €. This cluster constitutes the backbone of the French territory, structured by a tight network of small towns and villages.

Cluster C10: deep and stable rural. Cluster C10 groups 1,255 communes for approximately 693,000 inhabitants. Nature is very largely dominant (84.4%), lived density is moderate (1,313 hab./km²), local vitality is low (0.42), and macro centrality is limited (2.5). The residential stability rate is among the highest in the typology, and the approximated median income (22,151 €) is slightly below average. This is the most stable and isolated rural area, far from employment basins and large urban centralities.

Cluster C11: popular densified countryside. With an average lived density of 4,748 hab./km², a built density of 7.7%, and high macro centrality (11.6), cluster C11 is surprising for its intensity in an area classified as rural. Nature still represents 61.8% of the surface, but small towns and villages

are very concentrated. The approximated median income is rather low (22.045 €). This cluster brings together 3,628 communes for nearly 9.7 million inhabitants. These territories correspond to a densified *peri-rural* France, often at the interface with metropolises or mobility corridors, where residential density, local centrality, and social fragilities combine.

Cluster C9: specialized dynamic rural. Finally, cluster C9 aggregates 819 communes for a little over 526.000 inhabitants. Lived density is moderate (1,181 hab./km²), nature is dominant (72.5%), but local vitality is relatively high (0.85) and superior to that of other rural clusters. Macro centrality is low (2.2), while the approximated median income reaches 26.241 €, one of the highest levels. This profile refers to *specialized* rural territories (tourism, coastline, mountains, specific productive sectors), where economic dynamism does not mainly rely on proximity to a large metropolis but on its own activity.

5.6 Synthesis

The twelve-class typology highlights a fractal organization of the territory, where similar functional patterns are reproduced at different scales. It notably reveals: (*i*) a triply structured urban hierarchy (hyper-centers, secondary centers, pivot-cities); (*ii*) a diversified dense belt, opposing dense equipped suburbs, suburban rings, and dormitory spaces; (*iii*) a strongly polarized peri-urban, between wealthy peripheries and residential forest countryside; (*iv*) a plural rurality, far from the cliché of a uniform continuum. The simultaneous integration of form, amenities, and flows allows for the identification of territorial workings that would have been difficult to access through classical grid typologies or isolated communal indicators.

6 Conclusion and Perspectives

This work offers a first demonstration of the value of Graph Neural Networks for building a morphodynamic typology of French territories. By simultaneously articulating form (lived density, built texture, presence of nature), local vitality (amenities), and flows (residential migration, home-to-work mobility), the hierarchical model learns a latent space where proximity between communes is no longer defined by administrative contiguity, but by the similarity of their living conditions. Compared to classical approaches based on batteries of communal indicators or grid typologies, the proposed method presents three main contributions: (*i*) it explicitly exploits the graph structure of territories, integrating both topological relations and flows; (*ii*) it learns multi-scale representations that allow for aggregating micro information (inhabited cells) into coherent communal profiles; (*iii*) it produces an endogenous typology that can be reinterpreted a posteriori in geographical terms (centers, suburbs, peri-urban, ordinary rural, specialized rural, etc.). The empirical results show that the resulting typology goes beyond the urban/rural binary opposition by revealing twelve distinct profiles. This segmentation reveals a fractal organization of the French territory, in which the same functional motifs are declined across several scales. This initial exercise remains intentionally static: the set of variables used is fixed at a given vintage, and the graph only integrates a snapshot of flows. A natural perspective consists of extending the approach to the temporal dimension, either by stacking several years of data within a spatio-temporal GNN, or by studying the evolution of embeddings and clusters over time. This would allow for an analysis not only of territorial forms but also of their trajectories: metropolitanization, peri-urban diffusion, rural recomposition, effects of crises. Finally, the methodology could be declined in several directions: (*i*) specializing the graph on certain themes (access to healthcare, energy vulnerability, ecological transition); (*ii*) using the learned embeddings as explanatory variables in econometric models or supervised tasks (prediction of mobility, accessibility,

vulnerability); (iii) systematically comparing the resulting typology to other existing partitions (urban attraction areas, life basins, study zones) to evaluate convergences and discrepancies. Beyond the French case, this work argues more broadly for the use of graphs and GNNs in the analysis of territorial systems, in complement to traditional statistical and geographical tools.

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